

ISic1660

I.Sicily inscription 1660

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble (white)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.04.18

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Found on Capo Boeo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi, inventory 24361

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331219

1. ὁ δᾱμος
2. τῶν Λιλυβαιτᾱν
3. Διόγνητον
4. Δαματρῑου Μῆγα [ν]
5. εὐεργέταν.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284791

EDCS 64900328

PHI 331219

Bibliography

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